

DEMOKRITOS SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL

Foundations of Open Physics
Research: Inaugural Volume

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Journal Description:

Demokritos Scientific Journal: Open Access Research for Discovery is dedicated to advancing the frontiers of physics by providing an open platform for researchers across all disciplines of the physical sciences. We focus on ensuring the completeness and relevance of submissions through a thorough processing system conducted by expert area researchers. Our mission is to democratize scientific knowledge by making published papers searchable, discoverable, and accessible to a global audience.

While we do not engage in traditional peer review, each submission is carefully curated by specialists, categorized by research areas, and included in our journal for open review. Once published, papers are available for broad scrutiny and feedback, fostering a transparent and collaborative approach to scientific progress. By making research publicly available through the purchase of each journal volume, we support the free exchange of ideas and accelerate the discovery process across all branches of physics. Individual researcher papers will be available on networks like SSRN.

Key areas of physics that we will organize journal volumes:

1. **Theoretical Physics:** Quantum field theory, string theory, and other fundamental frameworks.
2. **Classical Mechanics:** Studies on Newtonian mechanics, Lagrangian and Hamiltonian formalisms.
3. **Quantum Mechanics:** Research on wave mechanics, quantum computing, entanglement, and quantum optics.
4. **Relativity and Gravitation:** Topics like general relativity, gravitational waves, and spacetime studies.
5. **Particle Physics:** High-energy physics, collider experiments, and studies on elementary particles.

Note: We will post details on the basic requirements with updates in this paper. Follow this paper on RG to receive notifications on future updates.

- 6. Condensed Matter Physics:** Research in superconductivity, semiconductor physics, and solid-state phenomena.
- 7. Astrophysics and Cosmology:** Research on dark matter, cosmic microwave background radiation, and galaxy formation.
- 8. Nuclear Physics:** Studies on nuclear reactions, nuclear decay, and applications in energy production.
- 9. Optics and Photonics:** Research on the behavior of light, laser physics, and photonic systems.
- 10. Plasma Physics:** Studies on plasma dynamics, fusion energy research, and magnetohydrodynamics.
- 11. Thermodynamics and Statistical Mechanics:** Research on entropy, temperature, and systems in equilibrium and nonequilibrium.
- 12. Applied Physics:** Studies with real-world applications, such as materials science, nanotechnology, and medical physics.
- 13. Biophysics:** The intersection of physics with biological systems, focusing on the structure and dynamics of biomolecules.
- 14. Computational Physics:** Research utilizing numerical simulations, algorithm development, and modeling of physical systems.
- 15. Acoustics:** Studies on sound waves, ultrasonic physics, and their applications.

These areas will serve as thematic focuses for different volumes or special issues, helping to expand research papers from each specific field. This approach will allow our journal to systematically cover a broad range of physics disciplines while organizing content in a clear, focused manner.

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The title “**Demokritos Scientific Journal: Open Access Research for Discovery**” was carefully chosen to honor the legacy of the ancient Greek philosopher **Demokritos**, often referred to as the “father of modern science” due to his foundational work on atomic theory. Demokritos proposed that everything in the universe is composed of indivisible units called atoms—a revolutionary idea that laid the groundwork for modern physics and scientific thought.

By invoking *Demokritos's name*, the journal symbolizes a dedication to exploration, innovation, and the pursuit of knowledge, just as he sought to understand the fundamental nature of reality. The inclusion of “Scientific Journal” ensures a broad focus on rigorous scientific research, while “Open Access Research for Discovery” reflects the journal’s commitment to making these findings accessible to all. This aligns with the principles of openness and discovery that Demokritos embodied, encouraging the sharing of knowledge without barriers.

The journal aims to foster a collaborative environment where scientific discoveries can flourish and be openly reviewed, allowing researchers from all corners of the globe to contribute to and benefit from the advancement of physics. The title not only pays tribute to one of history’s great thinkers but also reflects the journal's mission to support and democratize the dissemination of groundbreaking scientific research.

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